

Conflict Management Strategies Adopted by Principals in Administration of Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Dr. Ezenwagu Stephen Abuchi ¹
sa.ezenwagu@unizik.edu.ng

Dr. Nwamaka Florence Mokwe ²
nf.mokwe@unizik.edu.ng

Dr. Victoria Chimezie Mbonu ³
vc.mbonu@unizik.edu.ng

¹²³ Department of Educational Management and Policy, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka

Abstract

The study examined conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. From a population of 6,815 teachers, a sample of 1,363 teachers representing 20% of the population was drawn using a multistage sampling procedure. A researchers' developed instrument titled "Conflict Management Strategies Adopted by Principals in School Administration Questionnaire" (CMSAPSAQ) which was validated by three experts was used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured on a four point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha and this yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81, 0.78 and 0.76, for the three parts of the CMSAPSAQ and 0.78 for the entire instrument. The direct administration and retrieval method was used for data collection. A total of 1,363 copies of the questionnaire were administered while 1,240 were retrieved and was used for data analysis. Mean was used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study indicated that principals adopt six of the seven integrating conflict management strategies, five of the seven dominating conflict management strategies and five of the seven avoidance conflict management strategies in the administration of secondary schools. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the Government of Anambra State through the Post Primary School Service Commission should make provision for re-training of principals in the areas in application of conflict management strategies so as to help them update their skills and knowledge needed for managing conflict in the school.

Keywords: Conflict Management Strategies, School Administration, Secondary Education

Introduction

Education is an instrument for improving and developing one's potentials and skills, and in the process contributes to sustained well-being of the individual. This enables the individual contribute to the development of his or her community. Schools as important component of the

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 13 April 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15208615](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15208615)

education system, provide instruction and personality formation which enables economic progress and community development. There are different levels of education institution in Nigeria; among which is the secondary level which serves as a bridge between the primary school and higher institution. The principal is responsible for the administration of secondary school.

School administration is a social process concerned with identifying, motivating, controlling and unifying formally and informally organized human and material resources with a school. Iloh, Nwaham, Igbinedion and Ogogor (2016) defined school administration as the process of organizing and utilizing the available human and material resources for the attainment of educational goals. In the context of this study, school administration is the planning organizing and controlling the available resource in order to achieve set objectives of school. There are conditions of incompatibility or disagreement between two or more parties in the course of school administration which could cause conflict.

Conflict is any clash or disagreement in ideology, values and opinions of two or more persons. Conflict is inevitable in an organization but the ways it is managed can positively or negatively affects the behaviour and interpersonal relationships of members of staff in the school system. Conflict management is variety of ways by which administrators handle, respond to and deal with grievances before, during and after it has occurred. Mboya, Kiplagat and Yego (2017) defined conflict as a dispute, opposition or disagreements between individuals or groups of people. Mboya et al added that conflict occurs when people take opposing stands concerning issues and this can be expressed verbally or through actions. This indicates that conflict occurs when one party suggestion and interest is being opposed by another party. The researchers defined conflict as the disagreement or opposition between two or more parties.

Conflict is in inevitable in the school because the principal, staff and students have different ideologies, culture, value and role preferences. In other words, conflicts have become part and parcel of organizations including secondary schools and all other levels of educational institutions because individuals have varying ideas about issues, they have different backgrounds and their experiences are different. Arguing in the same line, Akinnubi, Oyeniran, Fashiku and Durosaro (2012) pointed out that it is obvious that conflict is inevitable, because it develops as a result of dealing with people's lives, jobs, students, pride, self-concept, ego and sense of mission or purpose. Mboya, Kiplagat and Yego (2017) stressed that as conflicts are inevitable, it is believed that there will always be disagreements among school administrators, teachers and students, but the disputes ought not to be left to get out of hand.

Conflicts may exist when students violate the school rules, students not doing manual work, students not respecting teachers, students engaging in vices like theft, fights, bullying or not attending lessons; teachers not respecting the principal or not completing curriculum, the principal's style of leadership demeaning teachers and disregarding students, among others (Mboya, Kiplagat & Yego, 2017). These conflicts have negative effects on the school administration; lowering teachers' morale, students' discipline and also hampering the general interpersonal relationships in an institution of learning (Ghaffar, 2008). Conflicts are not always

bad, the concern is how they are managed. When conflicts are constructively managed, they add value to the organization as opposed to when they are poorly managed; they turn destructive. Thus, conflicts need to be effectively managed for the proper functioning of any individual, group or organization (school). It is essential that principals adopt various conflict management strategies to prevent stress, unnecessary fatigue and tension in the school.

Several scholars have identified various conflict management strategies they include: integrating, dominating, avoidance, obliging and compromising (Kalagbor & Nnokam, 2015; Kilman, 2015). For the purpose of this study, the conflict management strategies that were adopted are integrating, dominating and avoidance. This justification for investigating these areas is because these strategies are rarely studied.

Integrating conflict management strategies involve openness, exchange of information, and examination of differences to reach a solution acceptable to both parties. Arguing in the same line, Kalagbor and Nnokam (2015) asserted that integrating strategy focuses on gathering and organizing information; at the same time, it encourages creative thinking and welcomes diverse perspectives. Kalagbor and Nnokam added that this strategy enable parties involve in conflict to pool all their information together, put their differences on the table and examine them along with any data that might contribute to a resolution. When principals adopt this strategy, they tend to be problem-centred rather than ego-centred which brings out transparency and honest in handling the conflict. It is a win-win situation which the both parties stand to gain. Integrating strategies encompasses high use of good communication networks, concern for others and an environment for discussion for exchange of information for resolving the conflict. There is shortage of information to resolve the conflict, principals may apply dominating strategies.

Dominating strategy is used by the school principal to resolve the conflict by dictating what the subordinates will do (Kalagbor & Nnokam, 2015). The results of this strategy benefit one party, because behaviour to get one's position is forced. In this strategy, one party wins while the other suffers from the humiliation of losing. In dominating strategy, administrators or individuals avoid other people's desires, expectations and needs so as to protect their own interest and attain their own goals. In this case, principals use their authority as head of school to reach decision with respect to resolving conflict without consideration of parties' views or opinions. Hellriegel and Slocum (2010) pointed out that this strategy is used in cases of high emergency where quick action is needed to make uncommon decisions, where action must be taken in the interest of institutional survival or effectiveness; or in cases where one person seeks to suppress others and quick actions need to be taken for protection of the interest of the institution. However, some principals may choose to adopt avoid managing the conflict instead of adopting dominating strategy which is characterized by use of force to resolve conflict.

Avoidance strategy is applied by principal who ignores conflicting issues or sometimes pretend as if there is no conflict in school. It is intentional withdrawing from the resolving conflict situations. In the view of Akuffo (2015), avoiding strategy is where parties to conflict sometimes pretend as if there is no conflict, stay away or withdraw from the substance of the conflict. In the

same vein This strategy is related to regression, dodging responsibility, sidestepping or no see, hear and talking the problem. However, under certain conditions, avoidance may not be the most appropriate ways of handling conflict as it may worsen or cause some damages in school. Crossfield and Bourne (2018) pointed out that this strategy may appear unappealing to teachers who may believe that the administrator is insensitive and thus the application of compromising strategies.

There is no single strategy that can be termed best for use by principals but the key to proper conflict management is to choose and execute the strategy that fits best in the situation at hand. Although, application of different conflict management strategies may lead to either desirable or undesirable outcome. Adhiambo and Enose (2011) stressed that effective conflict management strategy may result in desirable outcome such as smooth management, enhanced discipline, and effective management of time, team spirit, effective use of resources, achievement of goals, good relationships and great value by stakeholders. However, Adhiambo and Enose added that when ineffective conflict management strategy is used, undesirable outcome such as strikes, demonstrations, destruction of property, poor performance, emotional stress, misallocation of resources, absence and frustration may arise thus making the situation worse. Absenteeism, misallocation of resources and destruction of school property in the state seem to indicate the existence of conflict. There also seems to be cases of students not obeying school rules, engaging in vices like theft, fights, bullying, teachers' irregularity and punctuality to school and disrespecting the principal among others. This unsatisfactory state of affair makes it imperative to undertake this study to determine the conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

There seems to be occurrences of conflicts in secondary schools in Anambra State; simple issues as disliking a colleague, gossip, lateness, to more complex ones as role incompatibility, inferiority or superiority complex or leadership styles seems to be a source of conflict in secondary schools in Anambra State. Sometimes students engage in vices like theft, fights, bullying, absenteeism among teachers and disrespecting of principal among others. These forms of conflicts have the potential of advancing to more serious issues in the school. They seem to affect staff morale and feelings, decreases job effectiveness among staff, have direct effect on students' attitude towards their academic work which ultimately their achievement. Principals have to adopt conflict management strategies for putting them in check so that they do not unnecessarily cause physical, psychological or emotional exertions. It is in the view of the above that the researchers investigated the conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to ascertain the conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, this ascertained the:

1. Integrating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Dominating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools Anambra State.
3. Avoidance conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the integrating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools Anambra State.
2. What are the dominating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. What are the avoidance conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study which was carried out in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study. From a population of 6,815 teachers, a sample of 1,363 teachers representing 20% of the population was drawn using a multistage sampling procedure. A researchers' developed instrument titled "Conflict Management Strategies Adopted by Principals in School Administration Questionnaire" (CMSAPSAQ) which was validated by three experts was used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured on a four point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha and this yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81, 0.78 and 0.76, for the three parts of the CMSAPSAQ and 0.78 for the entire instrument. The instrument was considered reliable in line with Nworgu (2015), who stated that if the co-efficient obtained for an instrument is up to 0.70 and above, the instrument should be considered good enough to be used for a study. The direct administration and retrieval method was used for data collection. A total of 1,363 copies of the questionnaire were administered while 1,240 were retrieved and was used for data analysis. Mean was used to answer the research questions. A mean rating of 2.50 and above was interpreted as agree while mean rating of less than 2.50 was interpreted as disagree.

Results

Table 1: Mean ratings of principals on the integrating conflict management strategies they adopt in the administration of secondary schools Anambra State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Investigate conflicting issues before any resolution is made	2.65	1.07	Agree
2.	Clarify differences rather than accommodating different points of view in resolving conflict	2.45	1.18	Disagree
3.	Ensures fair solution in conflict situation	2.72	1.23	Agree
4.	Consults others in finding solutions to areas of conflict	2.54	1.13	Agree
5.	Encourage parties in the conflict to come up with alternative solutions and choose the most suitable one	2.71	1.22	Agree
6.	Constitute committee to handle conflicting issues in school	2.62	1.15	Agree
7.	Strives for a win-win situation in conflict management	2.55	1.08	Agree

Results in Table 1 shows the mean ratings of respondents on the integrating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools Anambra State. The respondents agree on six of the seven listed items as the integrating conflict management strategies adopted they adopt in the administration of secondary schools. The mean ratings for the six items ranged from 2.54 to 2.72. They however disagree on the remaining item (Item 2, mean 2.45) as being adopted in the administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: Mean ratings of principals on dominating conflict management strategies they adopt in the administration of secondary schools Anambra State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
8.	Dictate the solution to conflict in school	2.65	1.09	Agree
9.	Neglect the right of conflicting parties in taking actions toward resolving conflict	2.51	1.24	Agree
10.	Use threats to resolve solution	2.54	1.15	Agree
11.	Use force to handle disagreement among personnel in school	2.65	1.05	Agree
12.	Take actions without necessary observing due process in resolving conflict	2.40	1.10	Disagree
13.	Take side in a conflict situation	2.42	1.33	Disagree
14.	Instruct conflicting parties on what to do without consideration of the views	2.58	1.06	Agree

Results in Table 1 shows the mean ratings of respondents on the dominating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools Anambra State. The mean ratings of five (item, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 13) of the seven strategies were above the cut off mean of 2.50 indicating that principals adopt these five dominating conflict management strategies in the administration of secondary schools Anambra State. The remaining two strategies (item, 12 and 13) were not adopted by principals in the administration of secondary schools.

Table 3: Mean ratings of principals on avoidance conflict management strategies they adopt in the administration of secondary schools Anambra State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
15.	Withdraw in the process of finding solution to conflict in school	2.46	1.13	Disagree
16.	Sometimes pretend as if there is no conflict	2.65	1.02	Agree
17.	Ignores conflicting issues with the hope that would not become destructive	2.57	1.10	Agree
18.	Step side for conflicting parties to resolve their issues	2.48	1.13	Disagree
19.	Postpone conflict for better time in tactical way	2.72	1.06	Agree
20.	Set aside minor conflicting issues in school due to pressing administrative tasks	2.52	1.13	Agree
21.	Overlook conflict with the hope that it will go away	2.66	1.03	Agree

Table 3 shows that the respondents agree to five of the seven listed items as the avoidance conflict management strategies they adopt in the administration of secondary schools in Anambra State. The mean ratings for the five items ranged from 2.52 to 2.766. They however disagree on the remaining items (Item 1, mean 2.46 and item 18, mean 2.48) as being adopted in the administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of Findings

Integrating Conflict Management Strategies Adopted by Principals in School Administration

It was found that the integrating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State include; investigate conflicting issues before any resolution is made, ensures fair solution in conflict situation, consults others in finding solutions to areas of conflict, encourage parties in the conflict to come up with alternative solutions and choose the most suitable one, constitute committee to handle conflicting issues in school and strives for a win-win situation in conflict management. This is supported by the finding of Kalagbor and Nnokam (2015) which revealed that principals use the integrating conflict management strategies by conducting an investigating on causes of conflict, analyzing the information for the investigation, ensuring fair hearing and striving for the win-win situation. The similarity in findings could be attributed to geographical as the two studies were conducted in Nigeria in which similar laws guide management of conflict in school. Integrating strategies enable the principal to gather information, determine the alternatives and evaluations, and acting on the chosen decision to resolve conflict.

Dominating Conflict Management Strategies Adopted by Principals in School Administration

The result of the study revealed that dominating conflict management strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State include; dictate the solution to conflict in school, neglect the right of conflicting parties in taking actions toward resolving conflict, use threats to resolve solution and instruct conflicting parties on what to do without

consideration of the views. This is line with the finding of Fareo and Jajua (2018) which reported that dominating strategies adopted by administrators include; forcing conflicting to accept the solution to conflict, using of threat as means of settling conflict and making final decision to resolve conflict. The possible explanation for this agreement might be that in the same country and year. Observable changes might have not occurred in the same year. This finding suggests that principals could push conflicting parties view aside and impose the solution to the problem.

Avoidance Conflict Management Strategies Adopted by Principals in School Administration

It was reported that the avoidance strategies adopted by principals in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State include; sometimes pretend as if there is no conflict, ignores conflicting issues with the hope that would not become destructive, postpone conflict for better time in tactical way and overlook conflict with the hope that it will go away. This corroborates the finding of Adhiambo and Enose (2011) found out that avoidance strategies adopted by principals include; pretending as if there is no conflict, staying away from the substance of the conflict and dodging responsibility of managing conflict. School administrators apply avoidance strategies by dodging making important decision to resolve the conflict until the pressure is on, and in some cases resolve the cases at the last minute. In avoidance conflict management strategy, principals pretend as if there are no conflict situation schools. Avoidance conflict management strategies may not be a healthy approach to resolving conflict. Although, taking time to weigh the available options is a good idea, but avoiding resolving the conflict could result to negative outcome in the long run.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that principals adopt integrating, dominating and avoidance conflict management strategies in school administration in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Ministry of education should reach out to principals by organizing public lectures on the dominating strategies in handle some conflict situations at the shortest possible time.
2. Government of Anambra State should make provision for re-training of principals in the areas in application of compromising so as to help them update their skills and knowledge needed for managing conflict.
3. Government of Anambra State should embark on sensitization of principals on the application of avoidance through the media. Enlightenment should be given on the dangers of avoiding conflict management.

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